

LokAlp Mk I

Model	Mark I
Data	20/06/2023
Connections	15
Waste %	35.71%
Weight	8.10kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk II

Model	Mark II
Data	27/06/2023
Connections	23
Waste %	18.55%
Weight	8.80kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk III

Model	Mark III
Data	06/07/2023
Connections	37
Waste %	16.76%
Weight	6.09kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk IIIA

Model	Mark III/A
Data	09/07/2023
Connections	22
Waste %	20.47%
Weight	6.30kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk III_B

Model	Mark III/B
Data	09/07/2023
Connections	10
Waste %	20.81%
Weight	1.50kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk IV

Model	Mark IV
Data	20/07/2023
Connections	38
Waste %	27.73%
Weight	5.81kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk V

Model	Mark V
Data	23/07/2023
Connections	40
Waste %	28.19%
Weight	5.45kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk VI

Model	Mark VI
Data	11/08/2023
Connections	44
Waste %	25.66%
Weight	6.75kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk VII

Model	Mark VII
Data	12/08/2023
Connections	44
Waste %	22.58%
Weight	8.56kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp MK VIII A

Model	Mark VIII/A
Data	17/08/2023
Connections	44
Waste %	30.06%
Weight	7.73kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp MK VII_B

Model	Mark VIII/B
Data	17/08/2023
Connections	44
Waste %	29.52%
Weight	7.79kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk IX

Model	Mark IX
Data	05/09/2023
Connections	44
Waste %	24.16%
Weight	8.39kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk X

Model	Mark X
Data	07/09/2023
Connections	40
Waste %	23.91%
Weight	8.42kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk XI

Model	Mark XI
Data	07/09/2023
Connections	44
Waste %	21.83%
Weight	8.65kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

LokAlp Mk XII

Model	Mark XII
Data	13/09/2023
Connections	44
Waste %	30.85%
Weight	7.65kg

Top Scale 1:20

Side 1 scale 1:20

Side 2 scale 1:20

Bottom scale 1:20

Front - Back scale 1:20

